

MiMonte Project - Activities report under WP2, activity 2.a

2.a: Volunteers' reforestation day

1. Pego Reforestation day 1:

Date : 30th November 2025

Place : Pego

Time: all day

Number of Participants: 11

Number of trees planted: 150

OBJECTIVE:

The objective of the community tree planting day was to involve and educate community members about the importance and characteristics of their natural environment, the role and types of trees, and how to plant them and to create ownership and engagement of the local people in the project and foster increased care of their own natural environment.

TARGET GROUP

Local community members.

OUTREACH

- Email invites through Pego Viu network
- Publication through Desert Leaves' social media

METHODOLOGY / PROCESS

Information:

Participants received general information about the local natural environment, the impact of climate change, the recent fires that affected the area of reforestation and learned about the type of plants they were going to plant.

Demonstration:

The participants received a demonstration of how the trees should be planted in a proper way, and how the trees were going to be maintained.

Planting:

Participants worked together in planting the trees.

OUTCOMES

It was a very successful community engagement day, in which the participants planted 326 trees, and left with increased awareness, knowledge and ownership with regards to their own natural environment and particularly the reforestation project carried out by Desert Leaves and Pego Viu.

GALLERY

2. Ibiza. Voluntariado de Reforestación: Sustitución de marras e introducción a la biodiversidad del bosque mediterráneo

Date: 13/12/2025

Place: Cala Xarraca

Time: 10:00am-12:30pm

Number of participants: 20

Trees planted: 160

OUTREACH

- Instagram Post

OBJECTIVE:

To raise environmental awareness and teach participants how a Mediterranean forest is managed in order to improve the resilience of the Balearic territory.

TARGET GROUP:

Local community and land owners.

METHODOLOGY / PROCESS

The activity took the form of a hands-on working day in the forest, where participants collaborated in the replanting of species and carried out forest management and soil care tasks. The practical, real-work format allowed volunteers to engage directly with ecological restoration processes on the ground.

OUTCOMES

Participants engaged actively in ecological restoration work, demonstrating interest and commitment to the conservation and recovery of the natural environment.

GALLERY

3. Ibiza. Reforestation day with Families

Date: 21/02/2026

Place: Cala Xarraca

Time: 10:30am-12:30pm

Number of participants: 20

Trees planted: 40

OUTREACH:

- Instagram Post

OBJECTIVE:

To foster environmental awareness and encourage family participation in the conservation of the local ecosystem.

TARGET GROUP:

Families.

METHODOLOGY / PROCESS

The activity followed a participatory and educational methodology in which families actively collaborated in the planting of native species and the care of the natural environment. Throughout the session, the ecological functions of the Mediterranean forest and the importance of environmental restoration were explained, combining learning with hands-on action in direct contact with nature.

OUTCOMES

Participants responded very positively, showing enthusiasm, involvement, and a strong connection with the activity. The experience reinforced collective commitment to the protection and regeneration of the Mediterranean forest.

GALLERY

4.Fuente la Reina Reforestation Day with Volunteers

Date : 22/11/ 2025

Place : Fuente la Reina

Time: 13:30-15:30

Number of Participants: 37

OBJECTIVE:

To engage the local community and broader public in a collective tree-planting action contributing to the greening and ecological restoration of the Alto Mijares territory, while fostering a sense of environmental belonging and celebration through culture and music.

TARGET GROUP

Private land-owners in and around Fuente la Reina who own abandoned lands and the local community.

OUTREACH:

We have engaged the community through:

- Publication through Desert Leaves and Musica Pel Clima’s social media
- Website of Desert Leaves

METHODOLOGY

The event was structured in two complementary phases. In the morning (10:00–13:30), participants joined Desert Leaves and Tornem in a hands-on tree-planting session in the village surroundings, contributing directly to local reforestation efforts. Participants were asked to bring appropriate clothing, footwear, and work gloves. In the afternoon (13:30–15:30), the activity transitioned into a community picnic and live concert with Música pel Clima, combining ecological action with cultural celebration. The local social bar of Fuente la Reina offered a paella option for participants wishing to purchase lunch on-site. The event was free of charge and required prior registration via Eventbrite.

OUTCOMES

The event successfully brought together volunteers, local residents, and environmental advocates in a shared restoration and cultural experience. Trees were planted in the Alto Mijares area, contributing to the ongoing reforestation efforts in the territory. The live concert format with Música pel Clima helped frame climate action as a communal and joyful endeavour, reinforcing community identity around environmental stewardship. The collaboration between Desert Leaves, Tornem, Música pel Clima, and the Ayuntamiento de Fuente la Reina demonstrated the strength of multi-actor local partnerships.

GALLERY

